

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Biostimulants can partially replace inorganic fertilisers in conventional horticulture to keep high quality yields and reduce soil greenhouse gas emissions

During three years, we rotated in SE Spain (semiarid Mediterranean climate) the following crops: 1. Potato, from 22/12/2020 to 04/06/2021; 2. Broccoli, from 5/10/2021 to 10/01/2022; 3. Melon, from 29/03/2022 to 14/07/2022; and 4. Potato, from 16/12/2022 to 15/05/2023. The crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, where we reduced mineral fertilizer to partially replace it by biostimulants: i) Inorganic fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (F100); ii) The 50% of the rate of inorganic fertilizers added in F100 (F50); iii) F50 + the application of a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (BA); and iv).

F50 + the application of a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (BA+FU). The addition of biostimulants did not increase crop yields in any crops, but kept yields at the same

level of full inorganic fertilization. The addition of biostimulants did not affect broccoli and melon quality. However, it improved potato quality. Although size distribution and starch content showed no significant differences between treatments, BA+FU showed the highest mean weight and flesh firmness of tubers. In addition, the addition of BA+FU reduced the incidence of Rhizoctonia in tubers compared to full inorganic fertilization by 30%, improving the marketable value of the potatoes. Although soil physical and chemical properties were not affected by treatments, soil CO₂ emissions were reduced by 40% when adding biostimulants compared to full inorganic fertilization. Thus, the addition of biostimulants, mostly when plant growth promoted bacteria and fungi were added together (BA+FU), was positive to keep high crop yields, increase potato quality, and reduce soil CO₂ emissions. The use of biostimulants can be fostered in Mediterranean horticulture to reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers.

1. Potato crop under drip irrigation in SE Spain

KEYWORDS

Vegetables, rotations, biostimulants, soil, climate change, yield

AUTHORSHIP

Ollio, I., Fernández J.A., Sánchez-Navarro V., Lloret E., Egea-Gilbert, C., Martínez-Martínez, S., Zornoza, R.

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